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Peace Education in the Era of the 21st Century

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Abstract

*The majority of people desire happiness for themselves and their loved ones. In his book, *The Varieties of Religious Experience*, William James posed the following question: “What is human life’s chief concern?” ‘Happiness’ was one of the answers we discovered. Peace education is the most urgent requirement of the globe in the age of moral and character decay. Our country believes in “*vasudhaiv kutumbakam*”, so let peacebuilding be classed and defined as a skill in India’s NEP 2020 so that young can stand for peace and help to contain it for a worldwide peaceful society. In addition, Our National Education Policy 2020 also upholds our traditional Indian Values and heritage. All faiths include the following five values: “Truth, Peace, Nonviolence, Love, and Righteous Conduct” are the five universal ideals listed directly in NEP 2020. To combat global currently requires only one thing: peace content in curricula. We cannot make this world beautiful through a rat race to get good grades in exams; thus, it’s time to pay attention to the sole goal of education, which is “Peace, Love, character, care, and Happiness. This Paper discusses the concept and elements of peace education in the twenty-first century. The scholar emphasized the importance of cultivating peace education in youngsters through school curricula.*

Keywords: *Peace, Peace Education, Peace Transition, NEP-2020*

Introduction-

The concept of ‘peace’ is multidimensional. Peace is outlined vividly as a state wherever there is no hate, violence, conflict, disturbance, or hostility. It is referred to as the way of non-violent life, a state of harmony and tranquility. Peace can describe additionally a relationship between any individuals characterized by goodwill, justice, and respect. There’s not any concurrence relating to the definition of peace thus it’s been outlined in numerous ways. For instance, to Gandhi ji, peace is related to truth and non-violence. To achieve this state of ‘peace’, especially in the present conflict-ridden world, it is widely recognized that peace

education is an essential aspect that would guide mankind to shun violence and live in a harmonious world. It is being recognized as ‘an intellectual enterprise devoted to the study of peace and the bringing about of a state of peace in human society’ (John Baylis,) Peace education became a platform for the potential of hope for a better world Swami Vivekananda once said, ‘it is not man-making education, fifty years of such education has not developed one original man’. The result is that Man is missing from us. Existing education destroys those to whom it reaches; it destroys those to whom it’s denied. Actual education is an integral manifestation of universally inherent 5 components, viz, body, mind, vitality, intellect, and spirit in each boy and girl with no discrimination. If education is predicated on these 5 parts and practiced in-field and out of field education and until the tip of life everyone all over, justice will spread out peace will come out, and there will be no place of violence anywhere. The history of Peace Education has a rich history in India. The philosophies of various religions, and cultures, and their holy books like Geeta, Kuran, and the Bible proclaimed about peaceful society.

The National Education Policy 2020 additionally presents a singular chance to contribute to strengthening equity, justice, and social cohesion. The policy incorporates a broad concentration on value-based and experiential education, together with promoting essential thinking, cultural exchanges, teaching in regional languages, and a commitment to inclusion and education for all.

Concept of Peace Education:

Before understanding peace education we should understand the term peace the English word ‘peace’ is derived from the Latin word ‘pax’. Within the Roman Empire, Peace meant less conflict and more control over subject races. Definitions of peace through deterrence provide a modern parallel. Rather than focusing on what peace is, this definition focuses on what it is not. Peace education helps to improve relationships with others; thus, it is considered a relationship variable, not a trait. The concept of peace changes with respect to circumstances. Peace will be extended and dismissed according to circumstances. It depends on the people’s behaviors. Peace is not a passive state it is a vigorous method. Being passive isn’t a feasible path to peace. It takes active participation to build and maintain peace. Peace is tough to create and straightforward and easy to destroy. Peace takes many years to establish in our society, culture, and the hearts of people, but it is very difficult to maintain for a long time because small mistakes can ruin it.

The concern of peace education is to cultivate the elements of peace which helps students to solve their life’s problems and live peacefully in the world. Peace education is not only related to the classroom but also related to existing positive behaviors in academics and non-academic fields. James Page says that peace education is a commitment to the motivation of enhancing peace. And aware students, and scholars about the consequences of war as well as the importance of peace to the entablement of a peaceful society. Peace education is a kind of technique of getting the attitudes, values, skills, and information required for evoking changing behavior which can modify youngsters, youth, and adults to forestall conflict and violence.

The objectives of Peace Education:

Following exploration of the world of Peace Education, this study discovers these objectives:

- Appropriating intellectual and emotional development.
- Developing a sense of social duty and solidarity.
- Perceive the concepts of equality and fraternity in relation to everyone.
- Providing the individual with the ability to get a thorough awareness of national and worldwide issues.
- Developing a mindset for lifelong learning.
- Accepting and participating in open debates.
- Making decisions based on logic.
- Valuing the cultures of others; and
- Overcoming hurdles in the pursuit of peace.

Imparting Peace Education in School in the 21st Century:

To make this world beautiful, the Cultivation of peace education becomes very important to maintain peace in academics and non-academics, and at intervals serves as the world appears to become a lot smaller and virtually instantaneously, international problems are becoming native, and as a result, the responsibility of set up peace is not only the duty of social worker or reformer and government but also it's related to the curriculum of our schools and their teachers too, to imparting peace education in the soul and mind of the students and inculcate its elements within society and individuals. As a result, the importance of peace education has likely never been greater than the present. Peace education usually incorporates a broad background of non-violence analysis and determination, as well as an appreciation for diversity. Peace education could be taught in a variety of ways in universities, and it could be different in curriculum. It involves teaching peace, resolution of conflict, non-violence, human rights, environmental protection, and social justice (Smith 2004). Inculcation of Peace education in our school's curriculum is an important desire of our educational system. It begins with an open willingness to communicate with educators within the learning technique, which is a vital and effective way for them to rework themselves individually and collectively. The students want to be able to create and preserve peace. It will only evolve and grow as a result of your efforts. The following approaches will be used to deliver peace education:

- Organize extra remedial classes

- Focuses on the issues, violence, and peace breaker of classrooms and schools
- Imagining a more peaceful future

Practicing of Peace:

The aims of peace education are not successful until it is not engaged in the daily life of individuals. In the Indian context peace education in daily life means that type of education is helpful to increase inner peace. An American feminist philosopher Nel-Noddings (1998) argues that if we want to create a caring, loving, and peaceful society, we should focus on the practice of peace, care, and love. While practicing peace, we should inculcate the elements of peace in our daily life behavior, action, and dialogue, there are five essential elements of peace education – Positive relationships, cooperative learning, decision-making through constructive controversy, conflict resolution, and civic values. Practice of peace can be promoted through story writing and poetry writing competitions in schools, it may be helpful to motivate students towards peace and teachers can understand the thought process of students through these activities.

Conclusion:

In the age of crisis and war, where all mankind faces these types of problems, like war, brutality, fear, and feeling lessness, education for peace has become necessary. A peaceful life is more important than a successful life, success and peace are two different things because a peaceful person can live a successful life but it is not necessary for a successful person can live peacefully. So, education is the only way to cultivate peace, care, and love within students, In the rat race to achieve marks in examinations, our children lose their self-integrity and mindfulness, they lose their patience and forward towards a stressful life. As teacher educators and stockholders, it is our responsibility that we should provide our children with a good place for learning and tell them the true meaning of education. By teaching and practicing peace education to our coming generation we can make this world beautiful, so in the 21st century the chief concern of education must be peace, happiness, and care, these should be considered as the core objective of our education system.

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